

Research Data Management, Sharing and Reuse Practice in the Social Sciences: An Empirical Study

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Data Privacy and Consent Form

Thank you for your consideration of this survey. Please read the following information about the context of the study and provide consent if you agree to participate.

What is the purpose of this study?

This study investigates how researchers are curating, managing, sharing, and using research data in the Social Sciences and sub-disciplines. It also highlights the barriers and challenges faced by researchers in sharing and reusing research data. Moreover, it explores the factors influencing researchers' decisions to share or withhold their data. Information gathered from this study will help the research community gain a better understanding of current practices in the disciplines, such as the type of data more frequently produced, whether data reuse is common in the fields, and the type of policies and incentives needed to support researchers' needs.

This research has undergone rigorous review and has been granted ethical clearance by the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Development Studies Kolkata, in accordance with international research ethics protocols. The study adheres to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, ensures informed consent, protects participants' privacy and data confidentiality, and complies with the Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) guidelines by integrating gender-sensitive analysis where applicable.

The goal is to understand the data management, data sharing and reuse practice, with the following definitions.

Research data: Any information that has been collected, observed, generated, or created to answer novel research questions and validate research findings. Data may include any form of raw data, multimedia files, such as images, audio, video, codes, and software.

Dataset: A single file or a collection of data produced as a part of research and its associated metadata, such as an abstract, license, and any other relevant information that enables understanding and usage of the data in a legal way.

Research data management: Research Data Management (RDM) refers to the practices, strategies, and processes involved in the organization, storage, preservation, sharing, and reuse of research data throughout its lifecycle. It encompasses various activities, including data collection, documentation, storage, backup, security, data sharing, data publication, and long-term preservation.

Data repository: A data repository or data archive is a web-based infrastructure that hosts data in a secure manner and provides long term access to data. A repository can be a part of an academic institution or hosted independently (e.g. Zenodo, ICSSR Data Repository).

Data reuse: Any secondary use of data by users other than the data collectors.

Metadata: Structured information that describes various aspects of research datasets. These metadata serve as critical documentation and contextual information for the data, helping researchers, institutions, and data users understand, manage, and use the data effectively. Here are some key components and types of metadata related to research data:

Technical Metadata: Technical metadata focuses on the technical details of the dataset, such as:

File Format: The format in which the data is stored (e.g., CSV, JSON).

Data Size: The size of the dataset in bytes, kilobytes, megabytes, etc.

Data Structure: Information about the data's structure, such as tables, columns, and data types.

Data Quality: Information about data quality, including any known issues or limitations.

Descriptive Metadata: Descriptive metadata provides basic information about the dataset, including:

Title: The title or name of the dataset.

Creator(s): The individuals or organizations responsible for creating the data.

Date of Creation: The date when the data was generated or collected.

Abstract/Summary: A brief description of the dataset's purpose, content, and scope.

Keywords/Tags: Keywords or terms that describe the subject or content of the dataset.

Administrative Metadata: Administrative metadata includes information related to data management and access:

Data Ownership: Information about the organization or individual who owns the data.

Data Access Rights: Details about who can access, use, and distribute the data.

Data Usage Policies: Any policies or guidelines governing data use.

Data Versioning: Information about different versions of the dataset, if applicable

Provenance Metadata: Provenance metadata traces the lineage and history of the data, including:

Data Source: The source or origin of the data, including instruments, sensors, or data collection methods.

Data Processing Steps: A record of any data transformations, cleaning, or preprocessing.

Data Contributors: Information about individuals or entities who contributed to the data.

Organizations: They may include research institutions, universities and colleges with research departments, government research agencies, private research firms, non-profit research institutes, and more specialized organizations like think tanks or laboratories.

What information does the survey collect?

In this questionnaire, you will find a total of 37 questions divided into five sections. The initial section concentrates on gathering demographic information, encompassing your research area and level of experience. The subsequent section centers on data curation and

management. Following that, the third section is dedicated to data production and sharing practices. The fourth section delves into data reuse practices, and the final section explores incentives related to data utilization.

How long does it take to complete the survey?

The survey will take approximately 25-30 minutes or less to complete.

How will the information that you provide be used?

All identifiable information which is collected during the research will be kept confidential, but views and opinions given in the questionnaire may be published anonymously.

Any individually identifiable information, such as your name and email address, will not be disclosed or shared to any third parties and will not be released in any publications. To comply with data protection legislation, all sensitive data will be held on a password-protected computer and destroyed securely after December 31, 2026 upon completion of the study.

Permissions

Participation in this study is fully voluntary. You are free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason. If you withdraw from the study all the information and data collected from you, to date, will be destroyed and your name and email address removed from all the study files.

I confirm that I have read and understand the terms and conditions and agree to take part in the study.

YES		NO	
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Section-I: General Information

(Demographic Information including Research area and experience)

1) Please indicate your research experience in terms of years (A research career would normally start when a PhD starts). (Required)

- Up to 5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- More than 16 years

2) Please mention your area of research focus-

-

3) **Your current position/designation is:**

- Academic Administrator
- Assistant Professor
- Associate Professor
- Professor
- Post-doctoral Fellow
- Researcher (PhD)

- Research Associate
- Research Assistant
- Other (please specify)

4) Which of the following state/ union territory is your primary place of employment?

States:

- Andhra Pradesh
- Arunachal Pradesh
- Assam
- Bihar
- Chhattisgarh
- Goa
- Gujarat
- Haryana
- Himachal Pradesh
- Jharkhand
- Karnataka
- Kerala
- Madhya Pradesh
- Maharashtra
- Manipur
- Meghalaya
- Mizoram
- Nagaland

- Odisha
- Punjab
- Rajasthan
- Sikkim
- Tamil Nadu
- Telangana
- Tripura
- Uttar Pradesh
- Uttarakhand
- West Bengal

Union Territories:

- Andaman and Nicobar Islands
- Chandigarh
- Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu (merged into one Union Territory in 2020)
- Lakshadweep
- Delhi
- Puducherry
- Ladakh
- Jammu and Kashmir

5) Gender

- Male
- Female
- Third Gender
- Prefer not to say

6) Affiliation (Name of the University/College/other):

Section-II: Data Curation and Management

1) What type of data do you produce/use in your research? [Please give specific examples, e.g. survey data, type of samples/ observations.]

- Data models
- Experimental (involving some degree of manipulation)
- Interviews
- Observational (no manipulation involved)
- Remote-sensed data
- Machine generated data
- Social Survey
- Other (please specify)

[Definition of 'Research data' for reference]

Research Data: *Any information that has been collected, observed, generated, or created to answer novel research questions and validate research findings. Data may include any form of raw data, multimedia files, such as images, audio, video, codes, and software.*

2) What are the most important formats of data that you produce in your research? [Please select all that apply] Required

Please select at least 1 answer(s).

- Text
- Images
- Multimedia (Audio and/or Video)
- Software/ code
- Numerical data (Any type of quantitative measurements)
- Other

3) Have you created a data management plan for your current research? (*Please select all that apply*)

- Yes, it was a requirement of my current funder
- Yes, it was a requirement of my institution
- Yes, it is a requirement of the journal I plan to submit to
- Yes, but not as a result of any requirement
- No
- I don't know

4) The following group of statements relates to how do you collect and use research data. State us how much do you agree with each statement using the following scale: *strongly agree, somewhat agree, neither agree nor disagree (neutral), somewhat disagree, strongly disagree*

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	I don't know
I am satisfied with the process for collecting my research data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the process for searching for my own data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the process for cataloging/describing my data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the process for storing my data during the life of the project (short-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the process for storing my data beyond the life of the project (long-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the process for analyzing my data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I share my data with others.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Others can access my data easily.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I am satisfied with the tools for preparing metadata.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am satisfied with the tools for preparing my documentation.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

5) The following group of statements relates to how your organization is involved with your data. Tell us how much do you agree with each using the following scale: *strongly agree*, *somewhat agree*, *neither agree nor disagree (neutral)*, *somewhat disagree*, *strongly disagree*.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	I don't know
My organization or project has a formal established process for managing data during the life of the project (short-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My organization or project has a formal established process for storing data beyond the life of the project (long-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My organization or project provides the necessary tools and technical support for data management during the life of the project (short-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My organization or project provides the necessary tools and technical support for data management beyond the life of the	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

project (long-term).						
My organization or project provides training on best practices for data management.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My organization or project provides the necessary funds to support data management during the life of a research project (short-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My organization or project provides the necessary funds to support data management beyond the life of the project (long-term).	<input type="checkbox"/>					

6) The following group of statements relates to your views on the use of data across your research field. Tell us how much you agree with each using the following scale: *strongly agree, somewhat agree, neither agree nor disagree (neutral), somewhat disagree, strongly disagree.*

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	I don't know
Lack of access to data generated by other researchers or institutions is a major impediment to progress in science.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of access to data generated by other researchers or institutions has restricted my ability to answer scientific	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

questions.						
Data may be misinterpreted due to complexity of the data.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Data may be misinterpreted due to poor quality of the data.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Data may be used in other ways than intended.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Section-III: Data Sharing

- 1) Have you ever shared your research data by posting it on the web (e.g. in a data repository)? Required
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know/ Not sure
- 2) Do you curate/prepare your data for sharing during or shortly after the data collection process either privately or publicly?
 - Yes, all data collected
 - Yes, some of the data collected
 - Yes, but only data shared with colleagues or beyond
 - Yes, but only data shared publicly
 - No, it's not important with our data
 - No, we don't have the resource to do this but we would like to
 - No, other (please specify) _____
- 3) At which point during the research cycle, if at all, do you make your data available?
 - Immediately at the point when data is collected
 - When the research is complete
 - When submitting a research article
 - On publication of the research
 - Upon request from others
 - I do not share my data beyond my immediate collaborators

[Definition of 'Data repository' for reference]

Data repository: *A data repository or data archive is a web-based infrastructure that hosts data in a secure manner and provides long term access to data. A repository can be a part of an academic institution or hosted independently (e.g. Zenodo).*

- 4) How do you usually share your data? **[Please select all that apply]**
- Institutional repository (e.g., university repository)
 - Discipline-specific repository (e.g., Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR), PANGAEA)
 - Interdisciplinary repository (e.g., Figshare, Zenodo, Mendeley)
 - A journal supported repository (e.g., PLOS ONE)
 - Funder website/repository (e.g., [ICSSR Data Service](#))
 - Personal website/ Blog

- Cloud file sharing (e.g. Dropbox, Google Drive)
 - Other, (Please specify)
- 5) How did you first find a repository to share your data? Please select at least 1 answer(s).
- I was already aware of the popular/ relevant repositories in my field
 - Searched re3data.org (Registry of Research Data Repositories)
 - Web search
 - Consulted with colleagues or senior researchers
 - Consulted with the experts in my institution, e.g. Research data support services
 - Other (please specify):
- 6) To what extent do you think you make your data open in compliance with FAIR?*[Note: FAIR principles correspond to data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable]*
- Very much
 - Somewhat
 - Neutral
 - Not very much
 - Not at all
 - I don't know
- 7) Which of these factors influence your choice of repositories to share your data from?
[Please select all that apply]
- Discipline norms
 - Cost
 - Ease of use
 - Reputation of the repository
 - Appropriateness for data type
 - Data curation services offered
 - None of the above
 - Other
- 8) Do you know who meets the costs of making your research data openly accessible (e.g. resource for curation)?
- Own funds
 - Funds identified in your grant for this purpose
 - Your institution/organisation
 - Your funder

- General grant funds (i.e. those not specifically allocated to this purpose)
- I don't know

9) If your data are not available electronically to others (problems/concerns, if any, do you have with sharing datasets), why not (**check all that apply**)?

- Lack of funding
- Lack of standards
- Lack of technical compatibility
- People don't need them.
- Lack of time to make them available
- Data are too large to share
- Data are too little to share
- Concerns about misuse of data
- Not receiving appropriate credit or acknowledgement
- Others may find errors in my data
- I do not know what repository to use
- Unsure about copyright and data licensing
- There is no place to put them.
- They shouldn't be available.
- Sponsor doesn't require it
- Cost of data
- Don't have the rights to make the data public
- I have no desire to share my data
- Other (please specify)

Section-IV: Data Reuse

1) Have you ever reused existing datasets created by other people in your research?

Required

- Yes
- I only ever use my own primary data for my research
- My research doesn't use data
- I don't know/ Not sure

[Definition of 'Data reuse' for reference]

Data reuse:

2) Any secondary use of data by users other than the data collectors.

If yes, then mention—

Please select the best option that applies

- I use my own primary data but sometimes combine it with data from existing data sources
- I never use my own primary data but only ever use data from existing sources (e.g. datasets published in repositories) to answer new research questions

3) How do you find datasets to reuse? **[Please select all that apply]** Please select at least 1 answer(s).

- Search disciplinary repositories
- Search interdisciplinary repositories
- Web search (e.g., Google Dataset Search)
- Read relevant papers and then check if the authors shared data
- By accident – I noticed the dataset (e.g., in the original paper) and decided to use it.
- Colleague/Supervisor
- I don't know/can't remember
- Other

4) For which purposes do you reuse existing data? **[Please select all that apply]** Required
Please select at least 1 answer(s).

- Ground truthing: calibrate, compare, confirm (Comparative reuse)
- Analyze a single existing dataset to answer novel research questions (Integrative reuse)
- Combine multiple existing datasets to answer novel research questions (Integrative reuse)
- I don't know/can't remember
- Other

5) The following group of statements relates to data sharing. Tell us how much you agree with each using the following scale: *strongly agree, somewhat agree, neither agree nor disagree (neutral), somewhat disagree, strongly disagree.*

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	I don't know
I would use other researchers' datasets if their datasets were easily accessible.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would be willing to place at least some of my data into a central data repository with no restrictions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would be willing to place all of my data into a central data repository with no restrictions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would be more likely to make my data available if I could place conditions on access.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with my ability to integrate data from disparate sources to address research questions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would be willing to share data across a broad group of researchers who use data in different ways.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is important that my data are cited when used by other researchers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is appropriate to create new datasets from shared data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6) Are you familiar with the FAIR data principles in relation to open data?

[Note: FAIR data principles correspond to data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable]

- I am familiar with the FAIR data principles
- I have previously heard of the FAIR data principles but I am not familiar with them
- I have never heard of the FAIR data principles before now

7) Is each of the following conditions a fair exchange for the use of your data or a fair exchange for the use of other data?

	For others to use my data		To use other people's data	
	yes	no	yes	no
Co-authorship on publications resulting from use of the data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Formal acknowledgement of the data providers and/or funding agencies in all disseminated work making use of the data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Formal citation of the data providers and/or funding agencies in all disseminated work making use of the data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The opportunity to collaborate on the project (including, for example, consultation on analytic methods, interpretation of results, dissemination of research results, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Results based (at least in part) on the data could not be disseminated in any format without the data provider's approval.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
At least part of the costs of data acquisition, retrieval or provision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

must be recovered.				
Results based (at least in part) on the data could not be disseminated without the data provider having the opportunity to review the results and make suggestions or comments, but approval not required.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Reprints of articles that make use of the data must be provided to the data provider.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The data provider is given a complete list of all products that make use of the data, including articles, presentations, educational materials, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Legal permission for data use is obtained.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mutual agreement on reciprocal sharing of data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The data provider is given and agrees to a statement of uses to which the data will be put.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

8) To what extent are you comfortable with others using your data for the following?:

	Extremely comfortable	Somewhat comfortable	Neutral	Somewhat uncomfortable	Extremely uncomfortable	I don't know
Replication studies (use of your data as a reference to determine whether they can be repeated under similar conditions) (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reanalysis (using a different method to analyse your data set) (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reinterpretation (using your data as is to answer another question) (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Isolated reuse (reanalysing your data to answer a new question) (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Combination reuse (reanalysing your data in combination with other data sets to answer a new question) (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9) If you required help in making your research data openly available, which sources would you rely upon?(Please select all that apply)

- Open data software provider
- Colleague/Supervisor
- Web-search
- Institutional Library
- Publisher
- Funder
- Research office/In-house institutional expertise
- Professional 3rd party
- Repository
- Other (please specify) _____
- I would not require help making my data openly available

Measuring data reuse

10) Would you like to know whether someone else has reused your published data?

Required

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

11) Do you ever actively promote your published datasets? Required

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

12) How do you promote your datasets?

- In classrooms
- Using social media platforms
- Promote within research groups and collaborators' channels
- Other (Please mention)

Incentive

We are investigating the type of incentives that can improve the search experience and usage of research data. The following questions identify the factors that may assist in such decision-making process.

13) When searching for existing datasets, which of the following factors do you consider important for the decision to use one? **[Please select all that apply]**

- Proper documentation for the dataset

- The data is open (no application procedure)
- Information on the usability of the data
- Evidence that the data is from an associated publication
- The data is in a universal standard format
- Evidence that the data has been reused
- Other
- Not applicable

14) What type of information would be helpful in the documentation of a dataset? **Please select all that apply:**

- Type of data
- Subject of data
- Data collection method
- Other

15) How easy is it for you usually to find relevant datasets for reuse?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

Please select at least 1 answer(s).

How easy is it for you usually to find relevant datasets for reuse?

- Extremely
- Very
- Neutral
- Difficult
- Very difficult or often impossible
- I don't know/does not apply

16) What can be improved in current systems to encourage and promote data reuse?

Name:

Email:

Mob:

[End of Survey](#)

Survey questions end here. Thank you for participating in the survey. We greatly appreciate your time and input. If you would like to learn about the survey outcome then please submit your name and email address and we will be in touch upon completion of research.

If you have any questions about this study, the privacy statement, or data protection, please contact the researcher, who will be happy to assist you. You may reach us using the details below:

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